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CONTACTS

Phone: **97-748-70-03**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

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WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SOCIAL NETWORKS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

Kasimova Zilola Gulamiddinovna

PhD, Head of the Department of International Relations and History
in the non-governmental organization of higher education "Alfraganus University"
zilola.gulomiddinovna@gmail.com

Abstract: The rise of social networks and global digitalization has brought about significant transformations across various aspects of society, including tourism. The growing prominence of information platforms with traveler-generated content has shifted scientific research towards understanding the pivotal role of social networks in travel planning. Social networks increasingly influence tourist decisions regarding destinations, accommodations, and types of travel experiences. Typically, potential tourists are guided by engaging stories, vibrant images, reviews, public opinions, and other user-generated content available online. The article examines the impact of social networks, such as travel blogs and forums, on contemporary society.

Key words: travel blogs, forums, social networks marketing, business, internet.

INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions, the development possibilities of markets are influenced by the state of the macroenvironment, in particular the representativeness of the consumer segment and the conditions for building relationships with clients within the digital space. Macroenvironment factors largely determine the conditions and opportunities for business development in various industries and spheres. The marketing environment, especially its socio-demographic component, has a key influence on the development of tourism and, accordingly, the hotel business. Thus, the main demographic indicators allow us to judge the size and forecast values of the potential market, the popularity of the services offered based on the age and gender structure of potential consumers. Social criteria determine the popularity of certain price offers, value orientations and preferences based on the cultural level, education, familiar social environment and perceived needs for organizing everyday life, leisure, and needs. As researchers note, in the current global socio-economic system, certain trends in the influence of the macroenvironment are manifested, which are directly related to qualitative and, as a consequence, quantitative changes in the economy, technology, demography, and the social picture of the modern world [1]. The influence of any factors, including innovations, the formation of a knowledge economy, active population movement, the development of an entertainment economy, can have a number of positive and negative consequences for society as a whole and for tourism and the hotel business in particular [2]. Positive aspects of this kind usually include, for example, the population growth criterion, since with an increase in the population, the potential market of consumers of tourist services and the demand for accommodation services grows. A positive factor of influence can also include an increase in the life expectancy of the population, as well as an increase in the quality of life of adults and elderly individuals who tend to spend their leisure time, for example, getting new impressions during travel.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Positive changes for the tourism and hotel business are also dictated by an increase in the share of the elderly population, including the working population, who have certain formed desires and intentions that they can realize, having an appropriate income. In many ways, this is facilitated by progress in the development of medical technologies, since members of society can maintain a certain quality of life and spend their leisure time for their own pleasure. Along with this, such a direction as medical tourism is actively developing, attracting the "age segment" of consumers who prefer to combine rest with treatment and correction of their health condition. Another positive factor can be considered the population's focus on a healthy lifestyle, which contributes to the development of the organic food market and fitness club services. The same trend stimulates the development of active tourism, balanced loads during travel, etc. As one of the sub-directions in this direction, visiting "beauty farms" and various SPA-salons at famous resorts, on the territory of health resorts and simply outside the metropolises is developing, where services are offered to restore vitality, correct loads on the body, and restore

natural biorhythms. In many ways, this offer is focused on the female target audience, which has recently become economically active and can independently plan and pay for their vacation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The development of tourism and the hotel business is also positively affected by mass migrations of the population and modern communication technologies, which allow using booking services, information exchange, access to information about accommodation locations, estimated distances and reviews about them from industry professionals and consumers. A certain contribution to the noted processes is also made by the growing popularity of the second and third careers in the world, which implies both an increase in interest in receiving educational services abroad and subsequent foreign internships, in general, building one's own career in a country other than the country of primary residence. Nevertheless, along with many positive factors influencing the marketing socio-demographic environment, it can be noted that some of the changes occurring in society and the specifics of consumption can be attributed to negatively affecting and / or conditionally negatively affecting the development of tourism and the hotel business. Most of these factors, not directly, but indirectly, have a multifaceted impact on society and various spheres of its life. Thus, environmental standards for business make certain adjustments to work and increase the cost of various business processes, urbanization changes the "profile" of the planet as a whole, the lack of resources and time creates restrictions for full-fledged leisure and recreation of individuals, and the growth of consumerism and the strengthening of the role of consumer rights and protection create various difficulties for business, including tourism and hotel. It seems that the influence of factors of the marketing socio-demographic environment on the development of the tourism and hotel sector must be studied to identify certain patterns and build reasonable forecasts. In the context of digitalization of the economy, the population is adapted to receive information, including about hotel services, from Internet sources, spends free time and business communication on social networking sites, which, a priori, makes Internet marketing in demand in the work of hotel services. Currently, in the emerging modern digital economy, information and communication resources form a platform for the successful functioning of various organizations, building their relationships with business partners, conducting analytical work, monitoring market realities, marketing research of consumer preferences, reactions to new products and implemented bonus programs, etc. This platform, in principle, has made significant adjustments to the organization of communication promotion of products and the image of organizations, collecting and analyzing data, tracking the dynamics of consumer demand and organizing work with target audiences, which is extremely important for the sphere of functioning of hotel enterprises. In many ways, this circumstance is mediated by the fact that potential consumers of collective accommodation services are active Internet users. Thus, according to data from the annual Industry Report of the Federal Agency for Press and Mass Communications "Internet in Russia in 2017. Status, Trends and Development Prospects", more than 88% of young people, about 75% of middle-aged people; more than 50% of users aged 54 to 64; Among men over 65, every third person is an Internet user [3].

According to the data from the above-mentioned report, citizens of various age groups are active Internet users (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. U.S. Internet usage by income

According to the available research data, it can be noted that social status does not have much significance in terms of Internet use. Thus, “among managers and leading specialists, such people make up about 95%, among pupils and students – no less than 97%, among housewives – almost 88%, among the unemployed – about 70%; among pensioners – this is almost every third” [4].

Number of internet users in selected countries in 2022

(in millions)

Source: Enterprise Apps Today

Fig.2. Number of internet users in selected countries in 2022 (in millions)

Source: statista.com

DISCUSSION

We emphasize that the website of a hotel enterprise is a meeting place with potential clients and should initially interest them, and also have the most convenient and simple interface. It is very important to arrange all the important and relevant information for the consumer in such a way that he can immediately find it, that is, everything that the client needs should initially be placed on the main page of the site. It is also necessary to take into account that the results of empirical studies and measurements indicate that if the search time for the necessary information on the site for a potential consumer exceeds 30 seconds, the hotel enterprise risks losing the order of marketing allows hotel enterprises to fully implement activities within the framework of strategic, socially oriented marketing, relationship marketing, simplify research and building communications with the target audience, including a web resource and search engine optimization, Internet advertising, SSM marketing, SMS marketing, mobile marketing.

The clients of the hotel enterprise will positively evaluate the description of the objects located within walking distance from their location, especially if a map and step-by-step instructions are posted. It seems advisable to post a large number of photographs and/or video files that allow you to evaluate the proposed accommodation facility and the surrounding area. Another popular practical recommendation is to provide the contacts of the hotel managers in large print so that clients can easily clarify the current information on the availability of rooms.

Web resource and search engine optimization Information blocks containing information relevant to the target audience; tools for building interaction with target segments. The main task is to create demand and book rooms at the hotel enterprise

Internet advertising. Of interest to clients searching for hotel services; negative advertising does not cause rejection, since it creates the feeling that the client makes the decision himself without exerting intrusive communication pressure on him

Marketing in social media The emphasis is on attracting users of social networks to the website of the hotel enterprise, creating interest and drawing attention to the service products of the collective accommodation facility

Mobile marketing Involves bringing up-to-date information to clients and promptly receiving feedback from them, allowing to analyze emerging trends (for this communication you need a tablet, smartphone, mobile phone)

SMS marketing Is a component of direct marketing, allows to simplify the process of registering clients, notifying them of various promotions and client programs this is a form that assumes that the potential consumer will leave his contact information and he will be promptly called back to satisfy his request and help with the booking. Another important tool is the organization of consumer forums, where they can ask questions, describe their impressions, evaluate the services provided to them, clarify the reason for their doubts and / or concerns. Such discussion platforms are a valuable analytical resource for companies providing accommodation services. [5]

Social media plays a transformative role in tourism, influencing various aspects of the industry. Here's a summary of its key roles:

1. Travel Inspiration and Planning

Discovery: Social media platforms like Instagram, Pinterest, and TikTok offer visual inspiration for destinations, activities, and experiences. Travelers often use these platforms to discover new places and plan their trips based on posts and recommendations from other users.

Research: Travelers use social media to research destinations, accommodations, and attractions. Reviews, travel blogs, and user-generated content help in assessing the suitability of travel options.

2. Influence on Destination Choice

User-Generated Content: Photos, videos, and stories shared by other travelers influence prospective tourists' destination choices. Popular destinations often become trending due to the high volume of shared content.

Influencers and Reviews: Social media influencers and travel bloggers can significantly impact destination popularity through their endorsements and detailed reviews.

3. Marketing and Promotion

Branding: Tourism boards, hotels, and travel agencies use social media to market destinations and services. Platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter allow for targeted advertising and engagement with potential tourists. [6]

Campaigns: Social media campaigns and contests can create buzz and drive interest in specific destinations or events.

4. Customer Engagement and Service

Interaction: Social media enables direct communication between travelers and tourism businesses. This interaction can enhance customer service and provide real-time responses to inquiries and feedback.

Community Building: Businesses use social media to build communities around their brand, fostering loyalty and encouraging repeat visits.

5. Real-Time Sharing and Feedback

Live Updates: Travelers share real-time updates, experiences, and reviews during their trips, providing immediate feedback and influencing others' perceptions.

Reputation Management: Positive and negative reviews on social media can significantly impact a destination or business's reputation, highlighting the importance of managing online presence and responding to feedback.

6. Cultural Exchange and Connectivity

Cultural Sharing: Social media platforms facilitate the exchange of cultural experiences and stories, promoting cross-cultural understanding and appreciation.

Networking: Travelers connect with locals and other travelers through social media, enhancing their travel experience and expanding their networks.

7. Data and Trends Analysis.

Market Insights: Social media data provides valuable insights into travel trends, consumer preferences, and emerging destinations. This information helps businesses and tourism organizations tailor their offerings and strategies. [7]

In summary, social media has become a central element in modern tourism, shaping how travelers discover, plan, and experience their trips. It serves as a powerful tool for inspiration, marketing, customer engagement, and real-time interaction.

CONCLUSIONS

Given the current socio-demographic characteristics of the marketing environment, digital marketing is a valuable resource for the hotel business. Its importance as a communication platform for interaction with clients

and partners and an analytical platform for conducting research and further verification of the results obtained will increase, given the current level of development of the digital economic model in the country. Modern hotel enterprises need to competently analyze the innovations occurring in this area and adaptively implement them into their own business practices.

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